

Strip cropping

A SELF-GUIDED DOCUMENT
FOR FARMERS

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WHAT IS STRIP CROPPING?

Strip cropping is a farming method which involves cultivating multiple crops on one field in strips. Each crop is managed separately and therefore strip width and crop choice are important factors for the success of a strip cropping system. It's considered an accessible diversification strategy, because it can be adapted relatively easily to the needs of the farmer.

Currently, strip cropping is starting to be implemented all over The Netherlands. One of the advantages of strip cropping over sole cropping is increased biodiversity and decreased pest and disease pressure. Additionally, yields are maintained or even increased compared to sole crops (Figure 1). Management complexity and mechanisation are the current challenges strip cropping farmers and scientist are working on. In this document/module the most pronounced benefits and challenges of strip cropping will be briefly highlighted.

The following topics will be discussed:

- Crop choice & combinations
- Strip width
- Pest and diseases
- Mechanisation

[Introduction video strip cropping](#)

Figure 1. Relative yield of various crops at the Wageningen University and Research experimental fields in 2019. Yield is expressed as a relative value, meaning the absolute values of strip cropping and sole cropping are divided by the absolute value of sole cropping. If strip cropping yields are the same as sole cropping, the relative yield is 1. If the relative yield of strip cropping is 1.1, it means the yield in strip cropping was 10% higher than the yield in sole cropping. (Faber, Cuperus, & Apeldoorn, 2020)

MEET OUR EXPERTS

Dirk van Apeldoorn
Researcher at the Farming System Ecology group at Wageningen University & Research

Roy Michielsen
Staf employee at B.V. Exploitatie Reservegronden Flevoland (ERF)

Cornelis Mosselman
Organic Farmer & Owner of BI-JOVIRA

Arjen van Buuren
Organic Farmer & Owner of Landgoed Velhorst

Dirk van Apeldoorn: Webinar Strokenteelt Farm of the Future

Roy Michielsen: Movie about ERF Flevo Campus

Cornelis Mosselman: Strokenteelt bij de familie Mosselman

CROP CHOICE & COMBINATIONS

Crop choice is important for the functioning of a strip cropping system as the strip layout allows different crops to interact. At the border of a strip, where one crop ends and another begins, the different crops can influence each other. This influence can be both above and below ground and can be both negative and positive.

A well-known example of an above ground interaction is between carrot and onion. The carrot fly is repelled by the pungent smell of the onion. Therefore, carrot and onion are a good combination.

Maize and wheat have a below ground interaction. The maize roots wrap themselves around the wheat roots. In response to this competition, the wheat starts investing in stronger roots. This can result in higher yields compared to when the two crops are grown separately.

Both farmers and scientist have experimented with crop choice in strip cropping and collectively are starting to have a better idea which crops and crop combinations work well. In figure 2, the layout of one of the strip cropping fields from ERF can be seen. This particular field is designed to test which crops are good neighbours.

Figure 2. The spatial field layout at ERF to test which crops are good neighbours

STRIP WIDTH

The strip width is also an important factor in the functioning of a strip cropping system. Scientific research indicates that small strips of less than 3 meter in width are optimal. The close proximity of the crops ensures maximal interaction (like the ones discussed in crop choice and combinations) and better use of the available nutrients and sunlight. It seems the smaller the strip, the stronger the benefits of strip cropping (figure 3).

The current mechanization in The Netherlands is not (yet) adapted to this small working width. In most cases, the chosen strip width is wide enough for separate management of each crop using standard and available machinery. For example, if a farmer has machines with a working width of 6 meter, then the chosen strip width can be that. However, when smaller machines are available, it is recommended to use smaller strip widths due to the stronger benefits of strip cropping at those widths.

Figure 3. Graphical representation that with decreasing strip width more functions can be combined in strip cropping

PEST AND DISEASES

Strip cropping can result in better pest and disease suppression. Pest species can be better controlled by their natural enemies in strip cropping. Natural enemies are more abundant in the strips as they provide a continuous supply of shelter and food. This is due to the fact that the different crops have different growing periods, resulting in that the field is never completely bare. This can be further supported by careful crop choice, implementing flower strips in or around the field and having a green cover during winter.

Figure 4 provides an example of biocontrol in strip cropping. Juventia et al (2021) found that the feeding injury on cabbage decreased as the crop diversity in the field increased. More examples can be found in the following article (in Dutch): "[Biodiversiteit op de akker door gewasdiversiteit](#) by Wijnand Sukkel, Fogelina Cuperus en Dirk van Apeldoorn."

Figure 4. Relationship between crop diversity and feeding injury in cabbage. Crop diversity was measured by adding the number of species, accessions or cultivars in the design. In each graph, regression lines are shown; the respective equations are shown in the graphs. (Juventia, Rossing, Ditzler, & van Apeldoorn, 2021)

PEST AND DISEASES

The spread of diseases can be inhibited by the strip layout. The infection is contained to a single strip because a non-susceptible crop is in between the strips of the infected crop. Phytophthora in potato is a well-researched example. Ditzler et al. (2021) showed that Phytophthora spreads much slower in a strip cropping field than in a sole crop (Figure 5).

Additionally, the disease spread was also dependent on strip width. The smaller the strip, the slower Phytophthora spread throughout the field. Lastly, cultivating a mix of resistant and non-resistant potato cultivars in the strips further delayed the spread of Phytophthora. Due to the slower spread of Phytophthora in strip cropping, burning of potatoes can be delayed considerably by a range of 3 days up to more than 10 days.

PEST AND DISEASES

Figure 5. *Phytophthora* infection in potato over time during the 2017 growing season at the Wageningen experiment in the five treatments: large-scale reference monoculture (REF, grey circles), single cultivar 6 m strips (STRIP_6 m, green plus signs), single cultivar 3 m strips (STRIP_3 m, blue triangles), mixed cultivar 6 m strips (STRIP_MIX_6 m, yellow boxes), and mixed cultivar 3 m strips (STRIP_MIX_3 m orange squares). Large bold lines (a and b) show predicted infection per treatment calculated on mean rates modelled with a linear mixed effects model. Shaded transparent ribbons outlined by thinner lines (a) show the standard error of the predicted infection per treatment based on the model. The horizontal black dashed line (b) marks the infection threshold (20 infected leaflets per m²) at which potato fields must be burned, according to Dutch regulation. (Ditzler, Apeldoorn, Schulte, Tittonell, & Rossing, 2021)

MECHANISATION

Mechanisation is challenging in strip cropping. Although the strip width can be chosen based on the available machinery, some activities like irrigation, fertilization and spraying remain challenging. These activities are commonly done on a much larger scale, often full field, than for example sowing and harvesting. For example, a reel irrigates the entire field. However, not every crop requires the same amount of water. Even more problematic is when one crop requires irrigation, and its neighbouring crop is a grain almost ready to be harvested and thus needs to dry. Fortunately, many farmers have found solutions for these challenges:

Irrigation

- Section closure of an irrigation boom allows sufficient precision to only irrigate crops that need water. However, it is less efficient.
- Drip irrigation allows precise irrigation of the crops that need it. The disadvantage is that it is a large investment and might be damaged by mechanical weeding.
- Irrigation with hoses attached to a tank or boom allows to give controlled amounts of water close to the crops.

Fertilization

Practical experience of strip cropping farmers indicates that fertilization can be done efficiently in strip cropping systems. They commonly assume a full field basic fertilization with additional gifts in demanding crops.

Spraying

Spraying can be done in strip cropping using section closure. Important is to prevent spraying residues on neighbouring crops. It is important to review the spatial layout of the strips and crop choice to prevent residues and adapt your plan if necessary.

MECHANISATION

Other activities, like sowing, weeding and harvesting, are less challenging to implement in strip cropping. However, these activities also require careful planning. Take for example the harvesting of potatoes. This can require two machines, one to harvest and one to transport the potatoes. Therefore, the neighbouring strip is often used during the harvest. It is important to have a field layout where this neighbouring strip is either grass-clover or already harvested at the time of the potato harvest.

Despite these challenges, strip cropping is not considered to be less efficient. Organic farms like ERF did not indicate an increase in labour, while conventional farms expect to see a 20% increase due to less efficient spraying. In the case machines need to be purchased during the transfer from sole cropping to strip cropping, it's good to know smaller machines are usually also less expensive in purchase and energy costs. Additionally, GPS is highly recommended tool by strip cropping farmers that reduces the management complexity in a strip cropping field.

MORE INFORMATION

- A course is developed to support farmers with the development of their field layout and crop choice. Find more information on the course at www.bioacademy.nl (Dutch)
- [Strip cropping at Wageningen University & Research](#)
- [Strip cropping dossier](#) at Groenkennisnet (Dutch)
- [The ReMIX project \(Species mixtures for redesigning European cropping systems\)](#)
- [DiverIMPACTS - Diversification through Rotation, Intercropping, Multiple Cropping, Promoted with Actors and value-Chains towards Sustainability](#)
- [Website Cornelis Mosselman: www.vooruitboeren.com](http://www.vooruitboeren.com)
- [Website ERF: www.erfbv.nl](http://www.erfbv.nl)
- [Website landgoed Velhorst: www.landgoedvelhorst.nl](http://www.landgoedvelhorst.nl)

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